

M. Keshavarz, H. Hosseini-Nasab, M.B. Fakhrzad and H. Khademi-Zare. Problem data for “Impact of resource reconfiguration on the dairy supply chain resilience” (2024).

$i = 2$	$b = 4$
$t \cdot r = 12$	$s = 50$
$k = 11$	$j = 1$
CH_{jt}	<i>Uniform</i> (1000·1500)
CH_{jpt}	<i>Uniform</i> (500·600)
CH_{kpt}	<i>Uniform</i> (200·400)
Max_{jt}^{Iraw}	$Max_{jt}^{Iraw} = 3000$
Prc_{kmt}	$Prc_{k1t} = 7000$
CT_{jkpt}	<i>Uniform</i> (30·60)
CC_i	$CC_i = 100000$
TB_{jt}	$TB_{jpt} = 100000000$
V_{jpt}^s	<i>Uniform</i> (0·1)
V_{it}^s	<i>Uniform</i> (0·1)
HR_{jpt}^s	<i>Uniform</i> (0·1)
CT_{ijmt}	<i>Uniform</i> (30·60)
CT_{bjmt}	<i>Uniform</i> (30·60)
Prc_i	$Prc_i = 6500$
CAP_{irt}	$CAP_{irt} = \text{uniform}(10000,25000)$
CC_b	<i>Uniform</i> (400000·500000)
CAP_{krt}	$CAP_{krt} = \text{uniform}(10000,25000)$
	$\alpha_1 = 1$
	$\alpha_2 = 1$
	$\alpha_3 = 1$
α_p	$\alpha_4 = .5$
	$\alpha_5 = .5$
	$\alpha_6 = 1$
	$CE_{k1t} = 30000$
	$CE_{k2t} = 15000$
CE_{kpt}	$CE_{k3t} = 75000$
	$CE_{k4t} = 45000$
	$CE_{k5t} = 16000$
	$CE_{k6t} = 19500$
	$CAP_{j1t} = \text{Uniform} (18000 \cdot 22000)$
	$CAP_{j2t} = \text{Uniform} (3000 \cdot 5000)$
CAP_{jpt}	$CAP_{j3t} = \text{Uniform} (11000 \cdot 13000)$
	$CAP_{j4t} = \text{Uniform} (1500 \cdot 3000)$
	$CAP_{j5t} = \text{Uniform} (14000 \cdot 15000)$
	$CAP_{j6t} = \text{Uniform} (3000 \cdot 5000)$
	$CM_{j1t} = 8500$
CM_{jpt}	$CM_{j2t} = 10000$
	$CM_{j3t} = 4500$

	$CM_{j4t} = 3200$
	$CM_{j5t} = 9500$
	$CM_{j6t} = 12000$
Max_{kpt}^I	$Max_{k1t}^I = Uniform (250 \cdot 500)$
	$Max_{k2t}^I = Uniform (10 \cdot 20)$
	$Max_{k3t}^I = Uniform (75 \cdot 125)$
	$Max_{k4t}^I = Uniform (75 \cdot 125)$
	$Max_{k5t}^I = Uniform (200 \cdot 150)$
	$Max_{k6t}^I = Uniform (120 \cdot 160)$
dis_{ij}	$dis_{1j} = 4$
	$dis_{2j} = 6$
	$SL_1 = 4$
	$SL_2 = 7$
SL_p	$SL_3 = 7$
	$SL_4 = 7$
	$SL_5 = 9$
	$SL_6 = 3$
	$dis_{1j} = 12$
dis_{bj}	$dis_{2j} = 12$
	$dis_{3j} = 9$
	$dis_{4j} = 11$
	$CE_{j1t} = 9000$
	$CE_{j2t} = 10500$
CE_{jpt}	$CE_{j3t} = 5000$
	$CE_{j4t} = 3700$
	$CE_{j5t} = 10000$
	$CE_{j6t} = 12500$
	$Max_{j1t}^I = Uniform (1000 \cdot 2000)$
	$Max_{j2t}^I = Uniform (600 \cdot 800)$
Max_{jpt}^I	$Max_{j3t}^I = Uniform (1800 \cdot 2000)$
	$Max_{j4t}^I = Uniform (900 \cdot 1000)$
	$Max_{j5t}^I = Uniform (2000 \cdot 3000)$
	$Max_{j6t}^I = Uniform (500 \cdot 600)$
	$CL_{k1t} = 50000$
	$CL_{k2t} = 10000$
CL_{kpt}	$CL_{k3t} = 15000$
	$CL_{k4t} = 10000$
	$CL_{k5t} = 40000$
	$CL_{k6t} = 35000$
	$dis_{j1} = 28$
	$dis_{j2} = 18$
	$dis_{j3} = 22$
	$dis_{j4} = 24$
	$dis_{j5} = 18$
dis_{jk}	$dis_{j6} = 29$
	$dis_{j7} = 19$
	$dis_{j8} = 22$
	$dis_{j9} = 23$
	$dis_{j10} = 43$
	$dis_{j11} = 18$